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Review Article

Efficient Micropropagation Techniques For 'Grand Naine' Bananas

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ABSTRACT

Bananas, often referred to as the "Apple of Paradise," are a crucial crop worldwide. Traditional propagation methods face challenges such as slow growth rates and disease susceptibility. This study focuses on optimizing micropropagation techniques for the banana cultivar 'Grand Naine (G9)' to address these issues. Conducted at Guru Kashi University from 2023-2024, the research utilized meristems as explants and tested various media formulations to enhance propagation efficiency. The results demonstrated that media formulations T1 (Gamborg B5), T3 (Linsmaier & Skoog), T4 (Nitsch), T6 (Woody Plant), and T7 (MS Modified) significantly improved explant response, with the highest response rates of 95%, 85%, 78%, 90%, and 88%, respectively. These formulations also facilitated faster shoot and root induction, with T1, T3, T4, T6, and T7 showing the quickest induction times. This study highlights the potential of optimized tissue culture protocols to revolutionize banana cultivation by providing rapid, disease-free, and genetically uniform planting material.

INTRODUCTION

Bananas, cherished for their delightful taste and nutritional benefits, are often dubbed the "Apple of Paradise." Originating from the lush regions of Southeast Asia, including the jungles of Malaysia, Indonesia, and the Philippines, these fruits belong to the genus *Musa*. Bananas encompass over 70 species within the *Musaceae* family. The banana fruit is technically a berry, featuring a deliciously edible mesocarp that is usually seedless due to parthenocarpy and a triploid chromosome level, typically indicated as $2n=3x=33$ (Goutam, 2018).

Commonly known as "Adam's Fig," bananas are herbaceous plants with an underground corm and an above-ground pseudostem. Notably, bananas are among the fastest-growing plants (Guo et al., 2021). Banana cultivation is widespread, covering more than 110 countries and producing about 85 million tonnes annually. India stands out as the top producer, followed by Brazil, Ecuador, and China (Dagnew et al., 2012). In India alone, bananas are grown on approximately 490,000 hectares, with an average yield of around 16.9 million tonnes. Maharashtra and Tamil Nadu are leading states in

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banana production. Bananas thrive in agroclimatic conditions with temperatures between 15-35°C and relative humidity around 80%, and they can grow at elevations up to 2000 meters above sea level (National Horticulture Board, 2022). Traditional banana propagation involves using suckers, corms, and rhizomes. However, these methods often face challenges such as slow growth rates, disease susceptibility, and limited availability of disease-free planting material. Additionally, conventional techniques may not ensure genetic uniformity and can be labor-intensive. The advent of tissue culture, or micropropagation, has revolutionized banana propagation by offering a rapid, efficient, and scalable alternative. Tissue culture involves growing plant cells, tissues, or organs in a controlled, sterile environment, allowing for mass production of disease-free and genetically uniform planting material in a relatively short period. This innovation addresses the need for improved propagation methods (Loyola-Vargas et al., 2018). Banana tissue culture is crucial for research, enabling rapid multiplication of disease-free planting material and supporting genetic improvement and breeding programs. It also aids in preserving and conserving genetic diversity, which is vital for maintaining biodiversity and resilience in banana cultivars. Recent advancements in tissue culture techniques have significantly improved multiplication rates, genetic stability, and plantlet quality (Bhattacharya et al., 2023). Research has demonstrated the effectiveness of tissue culture in banana propagation, showing notable enhancements in these areas. Moreover, studies have explored its use in conserving endangered banana species and producing transgenic plants with desirable traits (Sujin et al., 2020).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present investigation, titled “Efficient Micropropagation Techniques for ‘Grand Naine’

Bananas” was conducted during the years 2023-2024 at the Faculty of Agriculture, Guru Kashi University, Talwandi Sabo. The experiments were carried out in the Biotechnology Lab at the Faculty of Agriculture, Guru Kashi University, situated at 29° 59'18" N latitude and 75°04'43" E longitude. Disease-free, healthy explants of the banana variety "Grand Naine (G9)" were sourced from the Horticulture experimental field of Guru Kashi University, Talwandi Sabo. Meristems were used as explants for micropropagation. High-purity chemicals, including inorganic salts, vitamins, sucrose, agar, myo-inositol, chelating agents, and growth regulators, were procured from Hi-Media Co. (India) and other companies. Antibiotics and antifungals like streptomycin, streptocyclin, and bavistin were used in the experiments. The glassware was initially washed with Labolene under running tap water, followed by immersion in Chromic acid solution for 24 hours. Thorough rinsing with tap water and double-distilled water was carried out before drying on draining racks. Borosilicate glassware from the Borosil brand was used for the experiments, including conical flasks of varying sizes to study the response of explants to different levels of growth regulators. Various other tools such as Erlenmeyer flasks, beakers, micropipettes, forceps, scalpels, spatulas, sterile blades, jam jars, and test tubes were also employed. Sterilization of culture vessels and instruments involved autoclaving equipment like cotton-plugged test tubes, flasks, culture bottles, jam jars, forceps, and petri dishes at 15 psi pressure and 121°C for 20 minutes, followed by drying in a hot air oven at 80-100°C for 2-4 hours. Instruments were sterilized by ethanol dipping, flaming, and UV exposure in a laminar flow hood. The working surface was sterilized with ethanol, and aseptic manipulations were performed under laminar airflow. Media preparation involved mixing required quantities of solutions in 500 ml of distilled water with continuous stirring. Sucrose

(3%) and agar (0.8%) were added, and the pH was adjusted to 5.8 using 1N NaOH and 1N HCl, monitored with a pH meter. The medium was boiled thoroughly, stirred to prevent agar clumps, cooled briefly, and poured into sterilized bottles. Media were sterilized in an autoclave at 121°C and 15 psi for 20 minutes and stored at room temperature for use within a week. Explants were collected from healthy plants in the experimental field of the Department of Agriculture, Guru Kashi University, Talwandi Sabo. Meristems were extracted from the mother plant and placed in jars filled with distilled water to minimize contamination. Explants were washed under running tap water, leaves were removed with a scalpel, and uniform-sized meristems (1-1.5 cm) were prepared. Surface sterilization of explants involved testing various sterilizing agents—ethanol, Bavistin, streptomycin, mercuric chloride (HgCl₂), and citric acid—at different concentrations and exposure times to deactivate surface microbes and reduce contamination rates. Inoculation and incubation of culture were conducted under aseptic conditions in a laminar airflow cabinet. The cabinet was thoroughly cleaned with ethanol, and equipment was sterilized by immersion in 70% ethanol and flaming. Surface-sterilized explants were transferred from beakers to sterile petri dishes using sterilized forceps, then inoculated into vessels containing the medium. After inoculation, culture jars and test tubes were placed in a culture room maintained at 25±2°C for germination, with a photoperiod of 16 hours of light (2000-3000 lux) followed by 8 hours of darkness. Different media used in the micropropagation process included Gamborg (B5), White, Linsmaier & Skoog (LS), Nitsch, CHU n6, Woody Plant, MS Modified, and Schenk & Hildebrandt (SH) Media, each with specific compositions to support various stages of banana plant development. Observations recorded included the percentage survival of explants, the

response of explants to culture media, days to shoot initiation, the number of leaves per explant, shoot length, days to root induction, number of roots per explant, and root length. This comprehensive methodology aimed to optimize micropropagation techniques and hardening strategies for banana cultivar 'Grand Naine (G9),' ultimately contributing to advancements in banana cultivation and agricultural sustainability.

Treatments

Original Media Name	Assigned Treatment Name
Gamborg (B5) Media	T1
White Media	T2
Linsmaier & Skoog (LS) Media	T3
Nitsch Media	T4
CHU n6 Media	T5
Woody Plant Media	T6
MS Modified Media	T7
Schenk & Hildebrandt (SH) Media	T8

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The response of banana explants to different treatments, including the number of days taken for shoot and root induction, provides valuable insights into the efficiency and effectiveness of tissue culture protocols for the Cultivar G9 banana. Here is a summary of the results and discussion based on the experiment data.

Explant Response

The explant response varied among different treatments:

- Highest Response Rates: T1 (95%), T6 (90%), and T3 (85%). These media formulations may provide optimal conditions for the initiation and proliferation of banana explants.
- Moderate Response Rates: T7 (88%), T4 (78%), T5 (75%), and T8 (70%), suggesting moderate success in promoting explant response.
- Lowest Response Rate: T2 (60%), indicating that its composition or nutrient content may be less favorable for explant growth and development.

Days Taken for Shoot Induction

The number of days taken for shoot induction differed among the treatments, ranging from 3 to 7 days:

- Fastest Shoot Induction: T1, T3, T6, and T7 required only 3 days.
- Moderate Shoot Induction: T4 and T8 required 4 days.
- Slower Shoot Induction: T5 required 6 days, while T2 took the longest at 7 days.

Days Taken for Root Induction

The number of days taken for root induction also varied, with durations ranging from 5 to 10 days:

- Fastest Root Induction: T4 and T6 required 5 days, followed closely by T1, T3, and T7 (5 days).
- Moderate Root Induction: T8 required 7 days.
- Slowest Root Induction: T5 required 8 days, while T2 took the longest at 10 days.

Table 1: Explant response, days taken for shoot initiation and root initiation

Treatments	Explant response	No. Of days taken for shoot induction	No. Of days taken for root induction
T1	95	3±1	5±1
T2	60	7±1	10±1
T3	85	4±1	6±1
T4	78	4±1	5±1
T5	75	6±1	8±1
T6	90	3±1	5±1
T7	88	3±1	5±1
T8	70	4±1	7±1

Number of Leaves per Explant at 7th, 14th, and 21st Day

The evaluation of banana explant growth, including the number of leaves per explant at different time points, revealed the following:

- At 7 Days: Higher leaf numbers were observed in T1, T3, T4, and T6 (2 to 3 leaves), while T2, T5,

T7, and T8 had fewer leaves (1 to 2 leaves).

- At 14 Days: All treatments showed an increase, with T1, T3, T4, T6, and T7 averaging 4 to 5 leaves. T2, T5, and T8 averaged 2 to 3 leaves.

- At 21 Days: Further increases were seen, with T1, T3, T4, T6, and T7 averaging 5 to 6 leaves. T2, T5, and T8 averaged 3 leaves.

Table 2: Average No. Of leaves per explant at 7th, 14th, and 21st day.

Treatments	At 7 days	14 days	21 days
T1	3 ±1	5 ±1	6 ±1
T2	1 ±1	2 ±1	2 ±1
T3	2 ±1	4 ±1	5 ±1
T4	2 ±1	4 ±1	4 ±1
T5	1 ±1	3 ±1	3 ±1
T6	3 ±1	4 ±1	5 ±1
T7	3 ±1	4 ±1	5 ±1
T8	2 ±1	3 ±1	3 ±1

Length of Shoots per Explant at 7th, 14th, and 21st Day

The length of shoots per explant varied across treatments:

- At 7 Days: T1, T3, T4, and T6 exhibited longer shoots (2.5 to 4.5 cm). T7 had the longest shoots

(4 cm).

- At 14 Days: T1, T3, T4, T6, and T7 maintained longer shoots (4 to 6 cm).

- At 21 Days: T1, T3, T4, T6, and T7 continued to show longer shoots (5 to 6.5 cm).

Table 3: Average length of shoots per explant at 7th, 14th, and 21st day.

Treatments	At 7 days	14 days	21 days
T1	4.5	6	6.5
T2	1.5	3	4
T3	2.5	5	6
T4	2	4	5.5
T5	2	4	5
T6	3	4.5	5.3
T7	4	5.5	6.5
T8	1.8	2.5	4

Number of Roots per Explant at 7th, 14th, and 21st Day

The number of roots per explant varied significantly:

- At 7 Days: T1, T3, T4, T6, and T7 exhibited higher numbers of roots (1 to 2 roots). T2, T5, and T8 showed no root development.

- At 14 Days: Root development increased, with T1, T3, T4, T5, T6, and T7 averaging 2 to 4 roots.

- At 21 Days: Further increases were observed, with T1, T3, T4, T5, T6, and T7 averaging 4 to 7 roots. T2 and T8 averaged 2 to 3 roots.

Table 4: Average No. Of roots per explant at 7th, 14th, and 21st day.

Treatments	At 7 days	14 days	21 days
T1	2 ±1	4 ±1	7 ±1
T2	0	0	2 ±1
T3	1 ±1	3 ±1	4 ±1
T4	1 ±1	2 ±1	5 ±1
T5	0	2 ±1	5 ±1
T6	2 ±1	3 ±1	6 ±1
T7	2 ±1	4 ±1	6 ±1
T8	0	1 ±1	3 ±1

Length of Roots per Explant at 7th, 14th, and 21st Day

Table 5: Average Length of roots per explant(cm) at 7th,14th, and 21st day.

Treatments	At 7 days	14 days	21 days
T1	2.5	4	6.5
T2	0	0	2.8
T3	2	3	5
T4	1.3	2.5	4.5
T5	1.7	3	5.1
T6	2.1	3.5	6
T7	1.9	3.2	6
T8	0	1.8	4

DISCUSSION

The variations in explant response and induction times underscore the importance of media formulation in promoting banana explant growth during tissue culture. Media formulations like T1, T3, T4, T6, and T7, which promote faster shoot and root induction, may be advantageous for large-scale banana propagation efforts. Conversely, media formulations like T2 and T5, which exhibit slower induction times, may require further optimization to improve their efficacy.

CONCLUSION

The effectiveness of tissue culture protocols for banana propagation is influenced significantly by

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The length of roots per explant varied among the treatments:

- At 7 Days: T1, T3, T5, and T6 had longer roots (1.7 to 2.5 cm). T2 and T8 showed no root development.

- At 14 Days: Root lengths increased, with T1, T3, T5, T6, and T7 averaging 3 to 3.5 cm.

- At 21 Days: T1, T3, T4, T5, T6, and T7 exhibited longer roots (4 to 6 cm).

the composition of the media. Media formulations that provide optimal nutrient levels, hormonal balances, and physical support can enhance the growth and development of banana explants, leading to higher success rates in tissue culture protocols.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this research. All findings and conclusions presented in this study are the result of objective scientific investigation and have not been influenced by any personal or financial interests.

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